

Estimation of Metal Complexes of Cysteine and Glutathione with Chloramine-T and Dichloramine-T**

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A simple and accurate method for the estimation of complexes of cysteine with the zinc group of metals, lead and palladium and glutathione complexes of silver, mercury and cadmium with chloramine-T and dichloramine-T at room temperature has been described. The direct titration with a visual or potentiometric end-point involves a one-electron change per molecule of the ligand in the complex. A back titration procedure in which the ligand is oxidized by excess of chloramine-T and dichloramine-T with a 10-electron change at pH 1 has also been developed. Amino acids such as methionine, threonine, serine and cystine interfere in the latter method, while only methionine interferes during direct titration of the thiol complex with the oxidants.

METAL complexes of cysteine (CySH) and glutathione (GSH) serve important functions in our biological system and play a dominant role in protein metabolism. They are important constituents of enzymes, proteins and are present in many parts of the biological systems.¹ Diuretic drugs such as 'mersalyl' are univalent mercurials, which are excreted as their cysteine complexes and they may act by combining with enzyme-SH groups in the kidney. Zinc complex is present in a number of enzymes and a protein containing Cd bound to SH groups has been isolated from horse kidneys.¹ In view of the importance of these metal complexes, it was found to be of interest to develop suitable analytical techniques for a quantitative estimation of these complexes. The authors have shown that pure cysteine² and glutathione³ undergo ready oxidation with chloramine-T (CAT) and dichloramine-T (DCT) under specified conditions. The present communication reports the oxidimetric estimation of CySH complexes with zinc group of metals, lead and palladium and GSH complexes of silver, mercury and cadmium with these oxidants. It was found that both direct titration methods and back titration procedures can be employed. A direct titration with a potentiometric end-point was however found suitable only with GSH complexes.

Experimental

Materials: Experimental details are described in the previous communications.^{2,3}

The following complexes of cysteine⁴⁻⁷ and glutathione⁸⁻¹⁰ were prepared by methods reported in literature.

- I. Zinc (II) Bis (L-Cysteinato) Zincate (II); $Zn [Zn(CyS)_2]$.

- II. Tetrakis (L-Cysteinato) trizinc (II) tetrachlorozincate (II). $[Zn\{Zn(HCyS)_2\}_2][ZnCl_4] \cdot 4H_2O$,
- III. Tetrakis (L-Cysteinato) tricadmium (II) tetrachlorocadmiate (II); $[Cd\{Cd(HCyS)_2\}_2][CdCl_4] \cdot 4H_2O$,
- IV. Mercury (II) bis (L-cysteinato) chloromercurate (II); $Hg[Hg(CyS)_2 HCl]$.
- V. (L-Cysteinato) lead (II), $Pb(CyS)$,
- VI. Bis (L-Cysteinato) Palladium (II); $Pd(HCyS)_2$
- VII. (Glutathionato) Silver (I); $Ag(SGH_2)$
- VIII. Mercury (II) (Glutathionato) mercurate (II) $Hg[Hg(GS)]_2$
- IX. Tetrakis bis Glutathionato (cadmate (II) $Cd[Cd(SGH)_2] \cdot 4H_2O$)

where Cy stands for $(CH_2.CH.NH_2.COO^-)$; $HCy = (CH_2.CHNH_2.COOH)$ and G is $^-OOC.CH(NH_2).CH_2.CH_2.CONH.CH.CONH.CH_2.COO^-$

The composition of the complexes was checked by elemental analyses. Solubility of the complexes in different solvents and buffers¹¹ was examined. Cysteine complexes are insoluble in water, but are soluble in NaOH and buffers of pH 1-3. GSH complexes are soluble only in pH 1 buffer.

Two methods were adopted for estimating the complexes:

(1) Direct titration method:

(a) *Visual end-point.* Preliminary investigations showed that solutions of CySH complexes in pH 1

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buffer with the exception of complex VI, can be directly titrated against 0.005 *N* CAT or 0.005 *N* DCT solutions with starch-KI as internal indicator. It was found that the stoichiometry of oxidation depended on the amount of KI present in the indicator. The amount of KI required varied with the individual complex and is as follows :

Complex I, 4.0-4.5 g (CAT), 4.5-5.5 g (DCT) ; II, 2.0-2.5 g (CAT), 1.0-1.5 g (DCT) ; III, 0.75-1.00 g (CAT), 0.40-0.75 g (DCT) ; IV, 1.0-1.5 g (CAT and DCT) and V, 1.75-2.50 g (CAT), 2.00-2.75 g (DCT).

It was found that the calculated yields of thiolic complexes were high when less KI is present than indicated above. However, no such dependence on KI concentration was observed with GSH complexes.

Recommended procedure :

Oxidation with CAT : Aliquots of the CySH or GSH complex solution in pH 1 buffer (5.0-20.0 mg) are taken in a 100 ml titration flask. About 1 ml of starch, and enough KI (40% aqueous solution) as indicated above are added. (Only a few drops of KI are sufficient for GSH complexes). About 10-20 ml of water are added and the solution is titrated against 0.005 *N* CAT to the appearance of a pale blue colour.

Oxidation with DCT : The procedure is the same as above, but the complex solution is to be diluted so that the total volume of the titrating solution is about 30 ml. This clearly shows that there is a small dilution effect, as was noticed in other cases.^{1,2}

(b) **Potentiometric end-point :** Although the standard electrode potential of thiol-disulphide system is only -0.25 v, a potentiometric titration of solutions of GSH complexes in pH 1 buffer with CAT and DCT solutions at room temperature was found possible in presence of added KI (~0.5 g). A potential break of about 100 mv, which was independent of KI concentration was recorded for a 0.1 ml addition of oxidant near the end-point.

If *x* is the amount (in mg) of the complex taken in an aliquot, then,

$$x = \frac{M}{E} N.V,$$

where *M* = Molecular weight of the complex, *N* and *V* are the normality and titre of CAT or DCT and *E* is the number of electrons changing per molecule of the complex.

2. Back titration procedure :

In preliminary experiments, known amounts of complex solution (~10 mg) in pH 1 buffer are added to a known excess of CAT (~1.0 m. mole) or DCT (~0.5 m. mole) in an iodine flask. The reaction mixture was set aside for various intervals of time, with occasional shaking. The excess of oxidant left un-

consumed was determined by back titration. The results showed that a 10 electron change per molecule of the ligand in the complex takes place, after 60 minutes in the case of complexes, I, II, IV, VI, VII, and IX, while the same stoichiometry is attained with complexes III, V and VIII after 90 min, with CAT. In DCT oxidations, complexes I, IV, V and VI require 60 minutes, while the duration is 90 min for complexes II and III. Oxidation of GSH complexes with DCT is sluggish and the required stoichiometry is attained after 120 min. with complex VII and after 150 min. with complexes VIII and IX.

Recommended procedure : Aliquots of the metal complex solution in pH 1 buffer (~5.0-22.0 mg) are added to 25 ml of 0.1 *N* CAT (or DCT) in an iodine flask. The mixture is shaken occasionally and after a known interval of time (mentioned above) 5 ml of 2 *N* H₂SO₄ (only in the case of CAT), 10 ml of 20% KI and 10-20 ml of water are added and the liberated iodine is titrated against 0.05 *N* sodium thiosulphate. A blank titration is carried out with CAT or DCT solution alone.

The amount (*x* mg) of the complex in the experimental solution is given by

$$x = \frac{M}{E} y (V_1 - V_2),$$

where *y* = normality of thiosulphate, *V*₁ is the blank titre and *V*₂ is the volume of thiosulphate used for the back titration. *M* and *E* have the same significance as before.

Results and Discussion

The results of direct titration of the thiolic complexes with CAT and DCT show that the ligand is oxidised to the disulphide stage with a one electron change. The stoichiometry is indicated for complexes I and VI, which serve as typical cases :

Where R = *p*-CH₃-C₆H₄SO₂,

R' = -CH(NH₂)COO⁻, and

G' = ⁻OOC.CH(NH₂)
CH₂.CH₂.CONH.CH.CONH.CH₂COO⁻.

The presence of the disulphide and *p*-toluene sulphonamide in the reaction products was detected by paper chromatography.^{2,3} The dependence of stoichiometry and rate on KI concentration, probably indicates that elemental iodine may be the reactive species, which brings about the oxidation of thiol (R₁SH) to

TABLE I

Estimation of metal complexes* of cysteine and glutathione with chloramine-T and dichloramine-T (visual end-point)
The amounts are expressed in mg.

I		II		III		IV		V		VII		VIII		IX	
Taken	Found	Taken	Found	Taken	Found	Taken	Found	Taken	Found	Taken	Found	Taken	Found	Taken	Found
Oxidation with CAT															
5.15	5.12	5.26	5.28	5.17	5.17	4.09	4.10	4.97	4.95	5.48	5.46	5.09	5.07	4.86	4.88
7.21	7.21	7.37	7.41	7.24	7.27	5.74	5.79	6.96	6.99	7.67	7.68	7.13	7.10	6.80	6.77
10.31	10.32	10.53	10.48	8.27	8.25	6.55	6.51	7.95	7.95	10.96	10.96	10.18	10.14	9.72	9.75
12.37	12.34	12.64	12.61	10.34	10.35	8.18	8.20	9.44	9.99	13.15	13.14	12.22	12.18	11.94	11.66
14.43	14.43	14.74	14.74	12.41	12.44	9.81	9.81	11.93	12.00	16.44	16.55	15.27	15.29	14.58	14.63
15.46	15.44	15.79	15.76	14.48	14.53	11.44	11.50	13.93	14.07	18.63	18.74	17.31	17.31	16.52	16.52
17.52	17.60	17.90	17.90	15.51	15.60	12.26	12.30	14.91	15.03	21.92	21.96	20.36	20.30	19.44	19.41
18.55	18.53	18.95	18.91	17.58	17.61	13.90	14.00	16.89	16.98	24.11	24.15	25.45	25.42	24.30	24.30
Oxidation with DCT															
5.16	5.17	5.26	5.26	5.18	5.16	4.09	4.07	4.59	4.61	5.44	5.46	5.60	5.60	4.86	4.86
7.22	7.27	7.36	7.39	7.25	7.23	5.74	5.79	6.43	6.40	7.62	7.62	7.84	7.87	6.80	6.82
10.32	10.34	8.42	8.45	8.29	8.33	6.54	6.48	7.35	7.34	10.88	10.92	11.20	11.20	9.72	9.72
12.48	12.43	15.52	10.51	10.36	10.39	8.18	8.2	9.19	9.22	13.06	13.06	13.44	13.48	11.66	11.68
15.08	15.44	12.62	12.64	12.43	12.45	9.81	9.87	11.02	11.11	16.32	16.36	16.80	16.81	14.52	14.58
17.54	17.60	14.73	14.71	14.50	14.52	11.44	11.52	12.86	12.88	18.50	18.56	19.04	19.01	16.52	16.54
18.58	18.54	15.78	15.77	15.54	15.55	12.26	12.28	13.78	13.83	21.76	21.82	22.40	22.34	19.44	19.44
20.64	20.74	17.88	17.89	17.61	17.68	13.90	14.01	15.62	15.73	23.94	23.94	24.64	24.61	24.30	24.30

* I, Zinc (II) bis (L-cysteinato) Zincate (II); II, Tetrakis (L-cysteinato) trizinc (II) tetrachlorozincate (II); III, Tetrakis (L-cysteinato) tricalcium (II) tetrachlorocadmiate (II); IV, Mercury (II) bis (L-cysteinato) chloromercurate (II); V, L-cysteinato lead (II); VII, (Glutathionato) silver (I); VIII, Mercury (II) (Glutathionato) mercurate (II); IX, Tetrakis bis (Glutathionato) cadmate (II).

disulphide as follows.^{1,2}

Some typical results of the direct titration are given in Tables 1 and 2. The results are reproducible within $\pm 0.8\%$.

The back titration results of the complexes with CAT and DCT show that oxidation takes place with a ten electron change, to the aldehydic stage. As typical examples, the stoichiometry for the back titration procedure can be shown in the case of complexes I and VIII as follows:

The presence of aldehydic amino acid HR'CHO in the reaction products of cysteine complexes was detected by paper chromatography ($R_F = 0.091$) using the amino acid developing solvent and spray reagent.²

TABLE 2

Estimation of metal complexes* of glutathione with chloramine-T and dichloramine-T (Potentiometric end-point).

The amounts are expressed in mg.

VII		VIII		IX	
Taken	Found	Taken	Found	Taken	Found
Oxidation with CAT					
5.35	5.40	5.76	5.77	2.45	2.45
10.69	10.68	11.52	11.55	4.09	4.09
12.83	12.86	13.82	13.77	8.22	8.23
16.04	16.07	17.28	17.32	9.86	9.86
18.17	18.21	19.58	19.65	12.33	12.35
61.38	21.43	23.04	22.98	16.44	16.44
Oxidation with DCT					
4.36	4.36	4.70	4.71	4.12	4.11
8.72	8.72	9.40	9.41	8.24	8.28
10.46	10.45	11.28	11.27	10.75	10.74
13.08	13.13	14.10	14.12	13.44	13.45
14.82	14.86	15.98	15.98	15.23	15.20
17.44	17.46	18.80	18.86	17.92	17.93

* VII, (Glutathionato) silver (I); VIII, Mercury (II) (Glutathionato) mercurate (II); IX, Tetrakis bis (Glutathionato) cadmate (II).

TABLE 3

Estimation of metal complexes* of cysteine and glutathione in pH 1 buffer with chloramine-T and dichloramine-T (Back titration)

The amounts are expressed in mg.

I		II		III		IV		V		VI		VII		VIII		IX	
Found	Taken	Found	Taken	Found	Taken	Found	Taken	Found	Taken	Found	Taken	Found	Taken	Found	Taken	Found	Taken
4.45	4.78	4.78	4.78	5.15	5.15	4.13	4.98	5.03	4.83	4.83	5.49	5.51	5.08	5.14	4.89	4.89	4.89
7.42	6.70	6.71	6.70	7.21	7.21	5.72	6.98	7.03	6.76	6.75	7.69	7.71	7.11	7.08	6.85	6.81	6.81
10.39	9.57	9.62	9.57	10.30	10.30	8.27	9.97	9.98	9.66	9.66	10.98	11.01	10.16	10.13	9.78	9.79	9.79
11.87	11.48	11.48	11.48	12.35	12.37	9.83	11.96	11.97	11.59	11.62	13.18	13.22	12.19	12.23	11.74	11.70	11.70
14.84	13.39	13.37	13.39	14.42	14.43	11.47	13.96	13.97	13.52	13.53	16.47	16.53	15.24	15.29	14.67	14.68	14.68
17.81	14.35	14.40	14.35	15.45	15.53	12.29	14.95	14.93	14.49	14.53	18.67	18.66	17.27	17.22	16.63	16.60	16.60
20.78	16.26	16.27	16.26	17.51	17.59	13.93	16.95	16.92	16.42	16.45	21.96	21.92	20.32	20.28	19.56	19.58	19.58
22.26	19.14	19.18	19.14	20.60	20.69	16.38	19.94	19.95	19.32	19.36	27.45	27.42	25.40	25.42	21.52	21.49	21.49
Oxidation with CAT																	
Oxidation with DCT																	
5.15	5.17	5.26	5.26	5.14	5.13	4.05	5.20	5.21	4.83	4.83	5.32	5.29	5.22	5.31	5.60	5.61	5.61
7.22	7.22	7.37	7.37	7.20	7.22	5.67	7.28	7.31	6.76	6.78	7.45	7.48	7.31	7.24	8.00	8.00	8.00
10.31	10.30	8.42	8.42	10.28	10.32	8.10	10.40	10.41	9.66	9.70	10.64	10.68	10.44	10.46	9.63	9.55	9.55
12.37	12.37	10.53	10.53	12.34	12.35	9.72	12.48	12.58	11.59	11.62	12.77	12.78	12.53	12.55	12.00	12.06	12.06
14.43	14.50	12.63	12.63	14.39	14.43	11.33	14.56	14.58	13.52	13.57	15.96	15.97	15.66	15.60	13.60	13.61	13.61
15.46	15.48	14.74	14.77	15.42	15.45	12.14	15.60	15.70	14.49	14.49	18.09	18.17	17.75	17.70	16.00	16.00	16.00
17.52	17.53	15.79	15.80	17.48	17.48	13.76	17.68	17.78	16.42	16.49	21.28	21.26	20.88	20.92	20.00	19.94	19.94
20.62	20.66	21.06	21.13	20.56	20.64	16.19	20.80	20.90	19.32	19.40	23.41	23.46	22.97	23.01	24.00	24.00	24.00

* I, Zinc (II) bis (L-cysteinato) Zincate (II); II, Tetrakis (L-cysteinato) trizinc (II) tetrachlorozincate (II); III Tetrakis (L-cysteinato) tricadmium (II) tetrachlorocadmiate (II); IV, Mercury (II) bis (L-cysteinato) chloromercurate (II); V, (L-cysteinato) lead (II); VI, bis (L-cysteinato) palladium (II); VII, (Glutathionato) silver (I); VIII, Mercury (II) (Glutathionato) mercurate (II); IX, Tetrakis bis (Glutathionato) cadmate (II).

The aldehydic tripeptide $H_2G'CHO$ was detected by paper chromatography⁸ as described for cysteine complexes ($R_F=0.39$). A single spot observed proves the absence of the hydrolytic cleavage of the two peptide bonds in the ligand.

Some typical results of analyses are shown in Table 3. The results are accurate within 0.8%.

It was found that the products of oxidation or the metallic ions at the concentrations employed did not react with the oxidants or oxidize KI under the experimental conditions.

The direct titration of palladium complex of cysteine with CAT and DCT was unsuccessful as it could not be oxidized at room temperature and the results were irregular when the compound was oxidized at elevated temperatures ($60^\circ - 70^\circ$).

Amino acids such as methionine, threonine, serine and cystine were found to interfere in the estimation of metal complexes of cysteine and glutathione during back titration but only methionine interfered in the direct titration of glutathione complexes.

It can be concluded from the investigations on metal complexes of CySH and GSH, that the number of ligand molecules present in a molecule of the complex, could easily be computed by oxidation with CAT or DCT.

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